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Research Article

Design and Evaluation of Fluconazole loaded *In-Situ* Gel for Ocular Keratitis

Ashwinkumar Budhanale*, Dr. Mangesh Bhutkar, Sangram Patil

Rajarambapu College of Pharmacy, Kasegaon, India

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ABSTRACT

Ocular keratitis, particularly fungal keratitis, remains a significant cause of visual impairment globally, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. Conventional ophthalmic formulations like eye drops often suffer from poor ocular bioavailability due to rapid precorneal elimination, tear turnover, and blinking. To address these limitations, the present research aimed to develop a fluconazole-loaded in-situ gel (ISG) using temperature-sensitive polymers for sustained ocular drug delivery. The study utilized Poloxamer 407, in combination with mucoadhesive agents such as xanthan gum and carbopol 934, to formulate a sol-to-gel system that undergoes gelation upon contact with physiological temperature. A 3² factorial design was employed to optimize the formulation based on critical parameters including gelation temperature, viscosity, and drug release profile. The optimized ISG formulation was characterized for clarity, pH, viscosity, gelation time and temperature, mucoadhesive strength, in vitro diffusion, and release kinetics. The antifungal efficacy of the optimized formulation was tested against *Candida albicans* and confirmed via agar diffusion studies. Additionally, the formulation exhibited sustained drug release, improved ocular residence time, and was found to be non-irritating in the HET-CAM test. Stability studies further validated the physical and chemical integrity of the formulation over a defined period. This study successfully demonstrates the potential of fluconazole-loaded thermosensitive ISGs as an effective, patient-compliant strategy for the targeted treatment of fungal keratitis, enhancing both therapeutic efficacy and drug bioavailability.

INTRODUCTION

Ocular drug delivery is one of the most challenging areas in pharmaceutical sciences due

to the complex anatomy and physiology of the eye. The eye possesses multiple protective mechanisms—such as tear turnover, nasolacrimal drainage, blinking reflex, and the tightly structured

*Corresponding Author: Ashwinkumar Budhanale

Address: Rajarambapu College of Pharmacy, Kasegaon, India

Email ✉: budhanalej@gmail.com

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corneal epithelium—which serve as efficient barriers to foreign substances, including topically applied drugs (1). These physiological barriers significantly reduce drug absorption and therapeutic efficacy, making it difficult for conventional ocular formulations to deliver therapeutic drug levels to intraocular tissues. As a result, less than 5% of the administered dose of eye drops typically penetrates to exert a pharmacological effect (2).

Among the various ocular conditions, fungal keratitis has emerged as a severe and potentially blinding infection of the cornea, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. It is primarily caused by pathogenic fungi, including filamentous species such as *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus*, and yeast-like organisms such as *Candida* species (3). These infections often result from trauma with vegetative matter, prolonged use of corticosteroids, ocular surface disease, or improper contact lens hygiene. The condition requires prompt and effective antifungal treatment to prevent progression and vision loss.

Fluconazole, a triazole antifungal agent, is widely known for its broad-spectrum antifungal activity, particularly against *Candida* species. It exerts its antifungal effect by inhibiting cytochrome P450-dependent 14 α -demethylase, an essential enzyme in the fungal ergosterol biosynthesis pathway (4). Despite its favorable pharmacokinetic profile and excellent penetration into ocular tissues, fluconazole's clinical use in ophthalmology is hindered by its rapid elimination from the ocular surface. Frequent instillation is required to maintain therapeutic drug concentrations, which adversely affects patient compliance and overall treatment efficacy (5).

To overcome these limitations, novel ocular drug delivery systems are being explored, with in-situ gels (ISGs) gaining considerable attention. These

are liquid upon instillation but undergo a phase transition to form a gel in response to physiological stimuli, such as changes in temperature, pH, or ionic strength (5). This phase transition not only enhances the retention time of the drug on the ocular surface but also provides sustained drug release, thus improving therapeutic outcomes and patient compliance.

Among the various types of ISG systems, thermosensitive in-situ gels are particularly promising. These formulations remain in liquid form at room temperature and gel upon contact with the ocular surface temperature (~35°C). Poloxamer 407, a thermoresponsive polymer, is widely used for this purpose due to its reverse thermal gelation properties. At lower temperatures, Poloxamer 407 exists as a free-flowing solution, but it transforms into a semi-solid gel at physiological temperatures owing to micellization and packing of its copolymer blocks (6). However, Poloxamer gels alone may lack sufficient mucoadhesive strength and mechanical integrity to withstand tear dilution and blinking forces. To address this, additional polymers like xanthan gum and carbopol 934 are incorporated. These polymers enhance viscosity, bioadhesion, and structural stability, resulting in improved ocular retention and prolonged drug action (7).

To systematically develop and optimize such a complex formulation, the 3² factorial design is a robust statistical approach. It allows for the evaluation of the interaction between multiple formulation variables and their influence on critical quality attributes. In this study, two independent variables—concentration of xanthan gum and carbopol 934—were varied at three levels to assess their impact on key parameters such as gelation temperature, viscosity, mucoadhesive strength, and drug release behavior.(8)

Objectives:

- To formulate an in-situ gelling system incorporating Fluconazole for the treatment of ocular keratitis, using suitable temperature sensitive polymers.
 - To improve the ocular residence time of Fluconazole by designing a gel that transitions when applied to the eye, it changes from sol to gel.
 - To improve the bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy of Fluconazole at the ocular site by overcoming challenges such as rapid tear drainage and low corneal permeability.
 - To assess the physicochemical characteristics of the ISG formulation, such as clarity, pH, viscosity, gelation temperature, and gel-forming ability.
 - To assess in vitro drug diffusion release behavior and determine the release kinetics of Fluconazole from the gel formulation.
 - To evaluate mucoadhesive strength and ocular irritation potential to ensure patient comfort and safety.
 - To test the antifungal efficacy of the formulation against common keratitis-causing fungal pathogens such as *Candida albicans*
 - Determine short time stability study of ISG of optimized batch.
- UV-Visible spectroscopy
 - Melting point of drug.
3. Preliminary study and development of Fluconazole loaded In-Situ Gel
 4. Characterization and Evaluation of prepared formulation
 - Clarity
 - Gelling Capacity
 - Gel Strength
 - Antifungal Activity
 - Stability Study
 - Rheological Studies
 - Gelation pH
 - Gelation temperature
 - Ocular Irritancy
 - Viscosity Determination
 5. Result and discussion
 6. conclusion.

Methodology

1. Selection of drug and excipients
2. Pre-formulation studies
 - a) Authentication of drug and polymer as per monograph.
 - b) Compatibility study of the drug and excipients by using following analytical tools.

Materials

Fluconazole was procured as the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) for antifungal activity. Poloxamer 407 (Pluronic F127) was employed as the primary thermosensitive polymer. Xanthan gum and carbopol 934 were used as mucoadhesive and viscosity-modifying agents. All other chemicals and reagents used in the study were of analytical grade and used as received without further purification.

UV visible spectroscopy

UV visible spectroscopy of Fluconazole in water

A) Calibration Curve of Fluconazole in water: Calibration curve of the Fluconazole carried in composition of DW at the λ_{max} 261

nm. The preparation of standard curve between absorbance and concentration.

Table No.1: Absorbance of Calibration Curve of Fluconazole in water

Sr. no	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance ± SD*
1.	0	0
2.	2	0.064±0.0032
3.	4	0.125±0.0023
4.	6	0.183±0.0015
5.	8	0.243±0.0011
6.	10	0.308±0.0017
7.	12	0.346±0.0031
8.	14	0.399±0.0024
9.	16	0.447±0.0019
10.	18	0.487±0.0023
11.	20	0.531±0.0028

UV visible spectroscopy of Fluconazole in STF

Calibration Curve of Fluconazole in STF pH 7.4:

standard curve between absorbance and concentration is shown in Figure no. 8.3 and values of absorbance are shown in Table No. 8.4.

Calibration curve Fluconazole carried composition of STF pH 7.4 at λ_{max} 261 nm. The preparation of

Absorbance values for the Fluconazole calibration curve were measured in STF at pH 7.4.

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance± SD*
1	0	0
2	2	0.058±0.0032
3	4	0.094±0.0023
4	6	0.147±0.0015
5	8	0.191±0.0011

6	10	0.248±0.0017
7	12	0.291±0.0031
8	14	0.323±0.0024
9	16	0.378±0.0019
10	18	0.421±0.0023
11	20	0.485±0.0028

FTIR Spectroscopy of Fluconazole:

Fig No 1: FTIR of Fluconazole

Table No 3. Result of FTIR Fluconazole

Observed Peak (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group	Type of vibration	Indication
3032.56	Aromatic ring	Stretching	C-H
2981.77, 2925.45	Alkyl group	Stretching	C-H
1590.78, 1507	Aromatic	Stretching	C-H
1383.61	Nitrate ion	Stretching	NO ₃

1279.56	Imidazole or ether ring	Stretching	C-N
1039.96, 1039.90	Possible ether or nitrate	Stretching/overlap	C-O/SO ₂
829.96, 721.56	Aromatic ring	Bending	C-H
625.65	Imidazole/benzene ring	Ring deformation	-

8.3.1.2. FTIR Spectroscopy of Poloxamer 407:

Fig No 2: FTIR of Poloxamer-407

Table No. 4. Results of FTIR of Poloxamer-407

Observed Peak (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group	Type of vibration	Indication
2880.33	Amide	Stretching	N-H
2742.89	Alkane	Stretching	C-H

2238.95	Nitrile	Stretching	C≡N
1644.5	Amide	Stretching	C=O
1464.19	Aromatic ring	Stretching	C=C
838.883	Aromatic ring	Bending	C-H

8.3.1.3. FTIR Spectroscopy of Xanthan Gum:

Fig No 3: FTIR of Xanthan Gum

Table No 5. Results of FTIR of Xanthan gum

Observed Peak (cm-1)	Functional group	Type of vibration	Indication
2918.73	Alkane	Stretching	C-H
1728.21	Carboxylic group	Stretching	C=O

1600.30	Aromatic ring	Stretching	C=C
1014.84	Ether	Stretching	C-O-C
780.14	Alkyl halide	Stretching	H-Cl

8.3.1.4. FTIR Spectroscopy of Physical Mixture

Fig No 4: FTIR of Physical Mixture

Table No 6. Results of FTIR of Physical Mixture

Observed Peak (cm-1)	Functional group	Type of vibration	Indication
2927.78	Aliphatic	Stretching	C-H
1733.91	Ester	Stretching	C=O
1154.74	Amide	Stretching	C-N
1378.89	Alkyl Halide	Stretching	C-F

1154.74	Ether	Stretching	C-O-C
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RESULT AND DISCUSSION :

Formulation of Fluconazole loaded in-situ gel batches:

In-situ gel technology shows promise as an effective formulation approach, especially for

water-soluble drugs like fluconazole. In laboratory settings, the cold method is employed to develop these ISG's. To prepare the ISG's, various concentrations of poloxamer 407 and xanthan gum were used. Poloxamer 407 was first dispersed in cold distilled water, after which xanthan gum was incorporated. Fluconazole was dissolved separately and then added to the xanthan gum mixture. Finally, the poloxamer solution was adjusted accordingly. The poloxamer solutions were partially hydrated and stirred at intervals until clear and uniform solutions were formed.

Fig. No 5: Formulation of FLZ-ISG using 3² Factorial Design

Fig. No 6: Optimized batch of FLZ-ISG

8.7 Characterization of final batches of FLZ-ISG using 3² full factorial design:

Table No 7. Final batches of FLZ-ISG using 3² full factorial design

Batches code	Drug (%)	Poloxamer-407(%)	Xanthan gum (%)	Gelation temperature(°C)	Gelation time (sec)	Drug Release (%)
FLZ1	300	16	50	37.5	140	95.52
FLZ2	300	16	75	36.3	105	92.34
FLZ3	300	16	100	34.6	73	88.83
FLZ4	300	17	50	34.8	75	92.81
FLZ5	300	17	75	33.8	65	88.2
FLZ6	300	17	100	32.4	60	85.01
FLZ7	300	18	50	33.2	60	88.51
FLZ8	300	18	75	32.3	65	83.9
FLZ9	300	18	100	30.2	75	80.23

Visual Appearance and Clarity:

The formulation of thermoreversible ocular ISG of Fluconazole was found to be clear (++) and

transparent at room temperature in liquid phase and also in gel form was found to be clear (++) and transparent. It is represented in following observation Fig. No 8.

Fig. No.7: Visual Appearance and Clarity

Table No.8: Visual Appearance and Clarity

Sr. No.	Formulation Code	Appearance of solution	Appearance of gel
1	FLZ 1	Transparent	Transparent
2	FLZ 2	Transparent	Transparent
3	FLZ 3	Transparent	Transparent
4	FLZ 4	Transparent	Transparent
5	FLZ 5	Transparent	Transparent
6	FLZ 6	Transparent	Transparent
7	FLZ 7	Transparent	Transparent
8	FLZ 8	Transparent	Transparent
9	FLZ 9	Transparent	Transparent

Fig.No.8: pH of optimized batch

pH

The pH of all ocular ISG of Fluconazole formulations was found to be in the range of 6.5–7.0 it is represented in following observation Table No. 8.22

Table No. 9: pH of All Formulation Batches

Sr. No.	Formulation Code	pH
1	FLZ 1	6.6
2	FLZ 2	6.5
3	FLZ 3	6.6
4	FLZ 4	6.8
5	FLZ 5	6.9
6	FLZ 6	7.1
7	FLZ 7	6.5
8	FLZ 8	6.7
9	FLZ 9	7.0

Viscosity

The viscosity of all ISG of Fluconazole formulations were measured by Brookfield Viscometer with spindle no. 62 at 100 rpm in before gelation and after gelation. It is represented as following observation Table No. 8.23

Table No. 10: Viscosity (cps) of All Formulation Batches

Sr. No.	Formulation Code	Viscosity of solution at 100 rpm(cP)	Viscosity of gel at 100rpm(cP)
1	FLZ 1	79.0	1109
2	FLZ 2	119.0	1265
3	FLZ 3	130.0	1582
4	FLZ 4	111.6	1267
5	FLZ 5	194.0	1987
6	FLZ 6	275.1	2840
7	FLZ 7	207.8	2165
8	FLZ 8	357.0	3234
9	FLZ 9	398.0	3889

Fig. No. 9: Viscosity (cps) of All Formulation Batches

Gelation Temperature:

The study of gelation temperature of all ocular ISG of Fluconazole was studied. It is determined in following observation Table. No. 8.24.

Table No. 11: Gelation Temperature of All Formulation Batches

Sr. No.	Formulation Code	Temperature (°C)
1	FLZ 1	37.5
2	FLZ 2	36.3
3	FLZ 3	34.6
4	FLZ 4	34.8
5	FLZ 5	33.8
6	FLZ 6	32.4
7	FLZ 7	33.2
8	FLZ 8	32.3
9	FLZ 9	30.2

Gelation Time

The study of gelation time of all ocular ISG of Fluconazole was studied. It is determined in following observation Table. No. 8.25.

Table No. 12: Gelation Time of All Formulation Batches

Sr. No.	Formulation Code	Time (sec)
1	FLZ 1	140
2	FLZ 2	105
3	FLZ 3	73
4	FLZ 4	75
5	FLZ 5	65
6	FLZ 6	60
7	FLZ 7	60
8	FLZ 8	65
9	FLZ 9	75

Fig.No.10: Gelation Temperature measurement

Eye irritation test: HET-CAM

Fig No 11: A sequence of images shows the changes on the membrane when treated with 0.9% saline solution (negative control) over a duration of five minutes.

Fig No 12: A sequence of images shows the changes on the membrane when treated with 1 M NaOH (positive control) over a duration of five minutes.

Fig No 13: A sequence of images shows the changes on the membrane when treated with B4 (test) over a duration of five minutes.

The HET-CAM test was conducted to assess the immediate irritant potential of the optimized

formulation FCZ 4 by observing any signs of irritation on the CAM membrane. The positive control (1 M NaOH) induced irritation, leading to bleeding and normal hyperemia, while the negative control (0.9% saline solution) exhibited no irritancy, maintaining normal tissue vascularization. When compared with these controls, it was evident that the optimized ISG formulation FCZ 4 did not trigger any inflammatory responses and preserved the normal vascular structure of the CAM tissue (arteries, veins, and capillaries). This indicates that formulation B4 is non-irritant and does not cause vascular damage.

This study confirmed that the optimized formulation FCZ 4 is safe and non-irritant, making it a promising platform for the effective delivery of Fluconazole to ocular tissues, particularly for Fungal Keratitis.

Antifungal activity:

The agar well diffusion method was used to assess the antifungal efficacy of FLZ-ISG formulations against *Candida albicans*. A standard fluconazole solution and a blank control were used to evaluate two test formulations, Sample A (FLZ 4) and marketed eye drop (ZOCON).

Each sample was evaluated at two concentrations (100 μ L and 200 μ L) to look for dose-dependent

antifungal effects. The formulation's efficacy in inhibiting fungal growth was demonstrated by the measurement of the zone of inhibition (ZOI) in nanometers (nm).

Visual Observations:

- 1) Sample A (FLZ 4) is displayed on the left petri plate, and Sample B (MCZ 5) is displayed on the right petri plate.
- 2) The wells holding the sample solutions exhibit distinct zones of inhibition.
- 3) As anticipated, the standard fluconazole (Std) has a noticeably greater inhibitory zone than the samples.

Fig.No.14. Antifungal Activity: A) Sample A FCZ And Marketed ZOCON

Table No 8.30. Antifungal activity by *candida Albicans*

Sr. No	Sample	Concentration	Zone of Inhibition(nm) <i>candida Albicans</i>	Observation
1.	Control		-	No antifungal activity (negative control)
2.	Standard Fluconazole	1mg/ml	15	Shows good antifungal activity (positive control)
3.	Sample-A	100 μ l	35	Strong antifungal activity
		200 μ l	7	Moderate increase in activity with higher dose

The antifungal activity results confirm that the FLZ-ISG formulations possess antifungal potential, with Sample A (FLZ 4) demonstrating better efficacy than (marketed eye drop ZOCON). This demonstrates that in situ gel formulations have the potential to treat ocular fungal infections, particularly when it comes to maintaining drug release and offering localized action at the infection site.

8.11.13 Stability study:

The stability study was conducted over a period of 30 days. The optimized formulation was stored in a stability chamber at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity, while room temperature conditions were also used for comparison. The study monitored the stability of the optimized formulation under these conditions, and the following observations were recorded.

Table No. 14: Stability evaluation of the optimized batch (FLZ4) conducted at $40 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity conditions.

Days	Appearance	Clarity	pH	Viscosity (cps)	Drug Content (%)
0	Transparent	Clear	6.8	1260	94.43
7	Transparent	Clear	6.8	1298	94.03
15	Transparent	Clear	6.9	1387	93.49
30	Transparent	Clear	6.9	1511	93.41

CONCLUSION:

A fluconazole-loaded in situ gel was effectively designed and optimized in this study utilizing a 3^2 factorial design to treat ocular fungal keratitis. Appropriate pH (6.8), fast gelation at physiological temperature (34.8°C), and sustained drug release with 92.81% drug diffusion were among the optimal formulation's ideal physicochemical characteristics. A non-Fickian diffusion mechanism and the Higuchi kinetic model supported the drug release, suggesting a combination of diffusion and polymer relaxation-controlled release. The formulation demonstrated significant antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*, The ISG was found to be a viable substitute for traditional eye drops in the therapy of fungal keratitis due to its overall superior ocular retention, extended medication availability, and increased patient compliance.

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